

Pragmatic Functions of Antenatal ... (Akande & Ogunfolabi, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15080365>

Pragmatic Functions of Antenatal Songs among Pregnant Women in Selected Antenatal Clinics in Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper identified and classified the themes of antenatal songs, examined how the themes are used to perform certain pragmatic functions and discussed how the themes are taught at the antenatal clinics in Ile-Ife. The study is qualitative research with a focus on antenatal songs. Using convenient sampling, the researchers selected Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC) and Health Centre at Oke-Ogbo which provided unrestricted access and enabled the researchers to attend and observe the clinics. Each hospital was visited three times to record the songs used at the antenatal clinics and a total of 14 songs were recorded, transcribed, and analysed for this study. The study made use of andragogy as its theoretical framework. Results showed that the themes of the antenatal songs are: family planning, prayers and encouragement, breastfeeding, nutrition and cleanliness and exercise. Results also showed that the pragmatic functions of the songs taught are: educating, encouraging, advising, entertaining, warning, praising and praying the songs were taught by the health practitioners, who take into consideration the fact that the pregnant women were adult learners. The study concluded that songs function as very good instruments for education and entertainment of pregnant women at the antenatal clinics.

Keywords: Antenatal songs, pragmatic functions, clinics, health practitioners, pregnant women

Introduction

Singing has always been part of the Yoruba culture. Yussuf and Olubomehin (2018) remark that what set Yoruba people and culture apart from other groups in Nigeria is their music which other genres of music such as *fuji*, *juju*, and *apala*. Songs perform a lot of functions among which include celebrating, admonishing, rebuking, educating and sometimes inciting people to take action. These songs can either be positive or negative but there is hardly any event in Yoruba land that is not accompanied by songs (Ogunlola 2013). According to him, singing is part of Yoruba culture and it is used to solve a whole lot of problems like hatred, threat to life and property, and killing of innocent citizens and also helps in ensuring conflict resolution and it enhances political economic, religious, and social stability. In essence songs constitute a vital tool for education in Yoruba land.

Giving birth to a child in Yoruba culture is a thing of joy that has always been celebrated and these celebrations have always involved the use of songs. However, before a new life comes into existence, especially in urban areas, there are some steps to be taken by the pregnant woman; such steps are usually taken to ensure safe delivery of the child and wellbeing of the mother. One of such steps is attending antenatal clinics. Antenatal clinic is a clinic specifically designed as a support system for pregnant women so as to educate, inform and keep guard the well-being of both the mother and the foetus so as to ensure a safe delivery. Ekabua, Ekubua and Njoku (2011:1) remark that antenatal care “is the care a woman receives throughout her pregnancy and is important in helping to ensure a healthy pregnancy state and safe childbirth”. Pregnant women are advised to visit the antenatal clinic immediately they discover that they are pregnant and make sure that they attend all sessions until they give birth. According to Thapa, Yadav & Bhujel (2016), antenatal care helps in early detection, treatment and prevention of complications that may arise during pregnancy. Consequently, good antenatal care can reduce neonatal and maternal death. Ekabua *et al* (2011) listed the main objectives of antenatal care among which are to promote the health of the baby, maintain the physical and mental health of the mother, develop birth preparedness procedure, provide complications readiness plan, and assist in preparing mothers to breastfeed successfully.

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One of the tools often used in the Yoruba-speaking states of Southwestern Nigerian antenatal clinics to prepare pregnant women for the birth of their baby is songs. Songs during antenatal clinics are used primarily to, *inter alia*, educate pregnant women. Education is very important for pregnant women because they need to know what to do, how and when to do some things that are vital for their well-being and that of their foetus. Educating adults especially pregnant women can be a herculean task. This is because adults are only interested in learning that is self-directed, practical and specific goal-oriented. In addition, they are less open-minded, slower to learn but able to integrate new knowledge to their past experiences and knowledge. Teaching pregnant women may be harder because of the physical discomforts that are noted to be associated with pregnancy which may decrease their attentiveness and the various myths that they might have heard which antenatal clinics may need to disprove. There is therefore the need for antenatal clinics to get creative while educating pregnant women. At antenatal clinics just before the pregnant women get to listen to health talks or see a doctor, the matron in charge of the clinic gets the pregnant women to stand up and sing various songs mostly in Yoruba language which is the dominant language of the environment. This study sets out to examine some Yoruba songs and the role(s) they play at antenatal clinic. It is against this background that the study seeks to identify and classify the themes of antenatal songs, examine how the themes are used to perform certain pragmatic functions; and also examine how the antenatal themes are taught.

Several works have been carried out on antenatal clinics (Thapa *et al*, 2016; Warri & George, 2020) , how pregnant women are cared for during pregnancy and different methods used in monitoring their progress (Titus, 2019). It is during this period that doctors and nurses provide appropriate advice and care to the expecting mother. Songs are an integral part of antenatal care in the Southwestern part of Nigeria while healthcare professionals are communicating with pregnant women. However, a crucial aspect that has not been fully explored is the use of Yoruba antenatal songs during the clinic and the pragmatic functions and the roles the songs play in achieving the goals of antenatal healthcare. Paying attention to songs such as these will help in determining the effectiveness of the songs as a crucial aspect of ensuring the good health of expecting mothers as well as the safe delivery of the baby.

The present study relies on andragogy as a theoretical framework. Andragogy is a theory of adult learning which was propounded by Knapp in 1833. The whole idea of the theory is that there is a great deal of differences between the ways adults and children learn and these differences need to be taken into consideration if effective learning must take place. The theory was promoted by Malcolm Knowles (Taylor & Kroth, 2009). According to McGrath (2009:102), andragogy “is centered on the idea that the lecturer does not possess all the knowledge and that students are encouraged to participate in the classroom by utilizing their own experiences”. For effective teaching of adults to take place, the instructor must not see himself as all-knowing who is dishing out instructions to learners but must rather guide learners to participate actively in knowledge production (Knowles *et al.*, 2020; Villegas, Yamamoto & Lloyd, 2021). Basically therefore, andragogy is about how adult learners process information they received based on such factors as their experience and motivation. Pappas (2023), popularising the theory further, states some principles that guide the way adults learn and it is these principles that mark adults learning different from children’s learning. The principles are as follows:

- a) Self-concept which deals with the way an adult view himself as opposed to how a child views himself. An adult is self-directed in his learning
- b) Experience which deals with the fact that an adult brings his whole gamut of experience and knowledge to bear in the teaching and learning process and this must be taken into consideration during the teaching and learning process.
- c) Readiness to learn which underscores the fact that an adult will be willing to learn when he understands the relevance of what he is learning. This means that there must be motivation and reward which can trigger learning. If an adult knows that if he learns a particular task or language, he or she could be promoted, such an adult will be ready to learn fast.
- d) Orientation to learning focuses on the need for adult learning to be practical, relevant and applicable for everyday life.
- e) Motivation to learn which emphasizes the fact that unlike a child, an adult is internally motivated to learn (Knowles 1984:12).

As with any theory, andragogy comes with its criticism. There are four main arguments against this theory. The first is the question of whether andragogy is a theory, a technique of adult education or just a set of assumptions because it cannot be measured empirically (Hartree 1984). The second is the confusion about what exactly are the procedures that make up the practice of andragogy (Rachal 2002). Also, there are questions on how to measure the effectiveness of andragogy since tests and grades are not encouraged for adult learners. Finally, the characteristics of adult learners are not all encompassing. A child

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may sometimes have a wealth of experience greater than that of an adult and there are some children who are self-directed in their learning (Merriam 2001 cited in Taylor & Kroth 2009).

Despite these criticisms of andragogy, it is popularly viewed as the theory of adult learning. Pregnant women going for antenatal care can be considered as adults because their age and social roles define them so. Antenatal care is to educate women so that they can have a healthy pregnancy and safe delivery (Ekabua *et al* 2011). The songs at antenatal care clinics underscore this message. This makes andragogy relevant and appropriate for this paper.

Methodology

The study is qualitative research with a focus on songs that are used in the selected antenatal clinics in Ile-Ife. The population for the study comprised all the antenatal songs used at antenatal clinics in Ile Ife. The sample for the study was a federal hospital and a health center in Ile Ife: Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex and Comprehensive Health Centre, Oke-Ogbo respectively which were selected through convenient sampling technique. The songs were recorded during the visits of the researchers to the hospitals. Each hospital was visited three times to record the songs used during the antenatal clinics and a total of 14 songs were recorded, and all the 14 songs were transcribed, and analysed in this study. Once the researchers realized that subsequent songs did not introduce new themes but were mainly variants or repetitions of the ones already recorded, there was conviction that the saturation point for the songs collected had been attained. Therefore, there was no need to collect more songs. The songs used in this study are designated as SG1 to SG14.

In this section, we discuss the themes, the way pregnant women were taught as well as the pragmatic functions of the antenatal songs that constitute the data for the study. For each of the themes, we provide example(s) of songs rendered in most cases in Yoruba with their translations in English. The themes of the songs are categorised and shown in the table below:

Table 1

Classification of Songs and Themes

Songs	Themes
SG1	Family planning
SG2, SG6, SG9, SG10, SG11, SG12	Prayers and encouragement
SG3, SG 14	Breastfeeding
SG5, SG7, SG8	Exercise
SG4, SG 13	Nutrition and cleanliness

Family Planning

One very important theme in the antenatal songs collected is family planning. Songs related to family planning are sung in order to encourage pregnant mothers to safeguard their health by going for family planning. This is very important in a country where there is an estimated 512 deaths per 100,000 live births and Nigeria accounts for about 34% of global maternal deaths (Adejoro 2022). Examples of such songs are:

SG1

Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Alábẹ̀rẹ̀ ñ bẹ ní sẹ́ntá	Song: Injections for family planning are available at the health centre
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Aláfibọ̀ ñ bẹ ní sẹ́ntá	Song: Intrauterine contraceptive devices for family planning are available at the health centre
Ègbè: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹ́bí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning

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Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Iṣu ti wọn, gàrí ò se rá,	Song: Groceries are very expensive
Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Song: Make use of family planning
Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Alátiṣe mātúnṣe ara rẹ	Song: A word is enough for the wise
Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning
Lílé: Bó bà fẹ kọmọ ó relé iwé,	Song: If you want your children to go to school
Ègbè: Fètó sẹbí rẹ o,	Chorus: Make use of family planning

The message in the song above (SG1) is on family planning. As could be seen from the content, the song performs the pragmatic function of advising parents about the need to reduce the number of children they may have by going for family planning. The advice is underscored by two important expressions: *Alátiṣe mātúnṣe ara rẹ* which translate to “A word is enough for the wise” and *Bó bà fẹ kọmọ ó relé iwé* which means “If you want your children to go to school”. There seems to be some negative perceptions about family planning especially with rural dwellers in Nigeria. This is not limited to the rural dwellers but there are also some religious sects, especially the Catholics that frown at family planning, maintaining that procreation should not be prevented (Abioje, nd). Saduki (2022) noted that only 22% of Nigerian women are favourably disposed to using family planning. SG1 is targeted at advising women who are not favourably disposed to family planning to have a rethink. There are 2 techniques of family planning used by women that are mentioned in the song to create the awareness that there are options available for them to prevent pregnancy. The first is that there are injections available at health centres to prevent pregnancy (*Alábéré ñ bẹ ní sẹntá*). The second is family planning technique is intra uterine device which are also available at health centres (*Aláfibò ñ bẹ ní sẹntá*).

Prayers and Encouragement

Nigeria is a very religious country and Osun State is a microcosm of the country in terms of its religious diversity. The recognition that pregnancy and childbirth can be perilous, coupled with the fact that the country is a religious one makes it necessary for antenatal songs to include words of prayer and encouragement for pregnant women. Following the belief that God is able to do all things, the antenatal songs can come in form of encouragement and prayers that the expectant mothers will come out hale and hearty after delivery. The speech act inherent in these songs is that of praying for both the mother and the foetus.

SG2

Lílé: Sẹwọ ni yóo bi o ?	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth this pregnancy.
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o. 2ce	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth this pregnancy.
Lílé: Bólú ọmọ keyọkan lókè,	Song: If there is just a glorious child left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bólú ọmọ keyọkan lókè,	Song: If there is just a glorious child left in heaven
Lílé: Sẹwọ ni yóo bi o?	Song: Will you be the one that will birth it?
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o.	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bólú ọmọ keyọkan lókè,	Song: If there is just a glorious child left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bí Nọ̀òsì keyọkan lókè,	Song: If there is just a nurse left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bí Dókítà keyọkan lókè,	Song: If there is just a doctor left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o,	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it
Lílé: Bí Lọ̀yà keyọkan lókè	Song: If there is just a lawyer left in heaven
Ègbè: Èmi ni yóo bi o.	Chorus: I will be the one that will birth it

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SG6

Lílé: È ba mi gbòṣùbà fòkò mi,
 Egbe: Ọkọ olórííre tó fún mi lóyúń.
 Lílé: È ba mi gbòṣùbà fòkò mi,
 Egbe: Ọkọ olórííre tó fún mi lóyúń.

Song: Join me to sing the praises of my husband
 Chorus: The wonderful man who got me pregnant
 Song: Join me to sing the praises of my husband
 Chorus: The wonderful man who got me pregnant

Lílé: Mo yá a gbòṣùbà fára a mi
 Egbe: Aya olórííre tó gbára dúró

Song: Join me to sing the praises of myself
 Chorus: The wonderful woman who eagerly performed her conjugal duties

Lílé: Mo yá a gbòṣùbà fára a mi,
 Egbe: Aya olórííre tó gbára dúró.

Song: Join me to sing the praises of myself
 Chorus: The wonderful woman who eagerly performed her conjugal duties

SG9

Mo ñ retí rẹ,
 Atinúkẹ mi,
 Atinúkẹ mi ò
 Á dé bá mi láyò. 2ce

I am eagerly awaiting you,
 My darling baby,
 My darling baby,
 You will get here safe and sound. 2ce

SG10

Lílé: Ọmọ tó wà nínú mi,
 Egbe: Ọmọ tó wà nínú mi,
 Lílé: Ó yá gbagbára Oluwa,
 Egbe: Ó yá gbagbára Oluwa,
 Lílé: Ó yá má a yíra padà,
 Egbe: Ó yá má a yíra padà,
 Lílé: O ò gbọdọ jókòó lódi,
 Egbe: O ò gbọdọ jókòó lódi
 Lílé: O ò gbọdọ nimí lára,
 Egbe: O ò gbọdọ nimí lára.
 Lílé: O ò gbọdọ gbẹmí mi
 Egbe: O ò gbọdọ gbẹmí mi.

Song: The foetus inside my uterus,
 Song: The foetus inside my uterus,
 Song: Receive the power from God,
 Chorus: Receive the power from God,
 Song: And turn your body
 Chorus: And turn your body
 Song: You must not be breeched
 Chorus: You must not be breeched
 Song: You must not cause me discomfort
 Chorus: You must not cause me discomfort
 Song: You must not cause my death
 Chorus: You must not cause my death.

SG11

Ó ní mà á bí wẹrẹ o
 Ó ní mà á bí wẹrẹ o
 Ọba mímọ kọ lẹtà sí mi,
 Ó ní mà á bí wẹrẹ.

He said that I will deliver my baby safely,
 He said that I will deliver my baby safely,
 The Almighty God wrote me a letter.
 And He said that I will deliver my baby safely.

The speech act in SG6 above is praising. Here, the pregnant woman is praising the virility of her husband and celebrating her fertility which resulted into the pregnancy. SG9 talks about the anticipation of the pregnant woman for the baby to arrive and prayers that the child will be delivered safely. SG10 addresses the foetus directly that it should receive power from God and not be breeched. The song beseeches the foetus not to cause discomfort to the pregnant woman and more important, must not cause the death of the pregnant woman. In SG 10 especially there is the pragmatic function of warning. The mother is warning the foetus not to cause her discomfort or take her life during the course of the pregnancy and labour. SG11 is composed in form of a letter received from God which assures the pregnant woman that she will deliver safely. SG12 is a wish from the pregnant woman not to look at her baby items and have the cause to lament. This alludes to praying for the baby's good health, praying that the baby will not be delivered as a stillbirth but to survive after it is born.

Breastfeeding

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The contents of SG3 and SG14 focus on breastfeeding and educating pregnant women on the importance of breastfeeding respectively. The lyrics of SG3 advises pregnant women to exclusively breastfeed their children for 6 months without giving them herbs or water. SG14 talks about the advantages of giving a baby breast milk exclusively because it makes a baby *fine* and free from all forms of diseases. This song is in line with the World Health Organisation's recommendation that a baby should be breastfed exclusively for six months.

SG3

Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle,
Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle,
Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn ɓòşù mɛɓà	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months
Lá láí fómí là,	Just breast to suckle without adding water
Lá láí fàgbo là,	Just breast to suckle without herbs
Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn ɓòşù mɛɓà.	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months

Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle
Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn,	Give your baby breast to suckle
Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn ɓòşù mɛɓà,	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months
Lá láí fómí là,	Just breast to suckle without adding water
Lá láí fàgbo là,	Just breast to suckle without herbs
Ma ɓomɓo lɔyàn ɓòşù mɛɓà.	Give your baby breast to suckle for six months

SG14

Lílé: Kí ló mómọ fine?	Song: What makes a baby <i>fine</i> ?
Egbe: Omú, omú, omú ni.	Chorus: Breast milk, breast milk, indeed breast milk!
Lílé: Kí ló mómọ nice?	Song: What makes a baby to be <i>nice</i> ?
Egbe: Omú, omú. omú, omú ni.	Chorus: Breast milk, breast milk, indeed breast milk!
Lílé: Kí ló mómọ fine?	Song: What makes a baby <i>fine</i> ?
Egbe: Omú, omú, omú ni.	Chorus: Breast milk, breast milk, indeed breast milk!

The speech act here is educating the pregnant woman about the importance of exclusive breastfeeding for the baby. SG14 is particularly acknowledging and advocating breastfeeding so that the baby can be 'fine'.

Exercise

Exercise is encouraged during pregnancy and this message is passed across through songs and pregnant women are made to stand up during these singing sessions and encouraged to dance as a form of exercise. The speech act here is encouraging pregnant women to exercise. Some of these songs require the expectant mothers specifically to touch some body parts as a form of exercise. The songs at antenatal clinics are generally designed to make pregnant women to sing and dance. This is so because exercise is believed to be good for a pregnant woman. Also, the singing and dancing are inundated with the Yoruba culture and these activities are found at almost every occasion in this part of the Nigeria.

SG5

Atínúkẹ̀ sẹ̀ ò ñ ri mi o,	My darling baby can you see.
Bí mo ẹ̀ ń ẹ̀	What I am doing?
Oyun inú mi sẹ̀ ò ñ ri mi o	My unborn baby can you see
Bí mo ẹ̀ ń ẹ̀	What I am doing?
Mò ń jò tapátapá,	I am dancing with both my arms
Bí mo ẹ̀ ń ẹ̀.	This is what I am doing
Mò ń jò ẹ̀şẹ̀şẹ̀	I am dancing with both my feet
Bí mo ẹ̀ ń ẹ̀. 2ce	This is what I am doing. 2ce

SG7

Òri mi, ẹ̀jìkà, ekún, ẹ̀şẹ̀,	My head, my shoulders, my knees, my toes,
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<p>Òrì mi, èjìkà, ekún, ẹ̀sẹ̀, Òrì mi, èjìkà, ekún, ẹ̀sẹ̀, Tirẹ̀ ni Oluwa. 2ce</p>	<p>My head, my shoulders, my knees, my toes, My head, my shoulders, my knees, my toes, All belongs to God. 2ce</p>
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SG8

<p>Lílẹ̀: Ẹ̀ bá mi gbòndò yí gbẹ̀, Egbe: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala, Lílẹ̀: Ẹ̀ bá mi gbòndò yí gbẹ̀, Egbe: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala,</p>	<p>Song: Join me to drain this river Chorus: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala, Song: Join me to drain this river Chorus: Jangbala jùgbù, ijùgbù, ijùgbù jangbala,</p>
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SG7 as seen above is a nursery rhyme that is used to teach children their body parts while SG8 is a chorus of a popular folklore in Yoruba moonlight story culture. Both songs are meant to encourage women to exercise and at the same time entertain them. The speech act of both songs can be said to be entertainment.

Nutrition and Cleanliness

The diet of a pregnant woman is very important and antenatal clinics use songs as a vehicle to pass across this message. SG 4 emphasizes the importance of eating nutritious meal especially food items like eggs and meat that are high in protein for the well-being of the baby. The foetus is described as a piggy bank where nutritious meals are kept and which will be harvested on the day the baby is delivered. Here, it is implied that eating nutritious meals will make the baby to be healthy, and also for the mother to have a safe delivery, and a quick recovery after giving birth to the baby.

SG4

<p>Bí mo réyìn ma rà fọ́yún mi jẹ̀ Bí mo réja ma rà fọ́yún mi jẹ̀ Ìnu báńkì tí mó òn pawó sí Lójò ikúnlẹ̀ lẹ̀mi ó ko. Bí mo réyìn ma rà fọ́yún mi jẹ̀, Bí mo réja ma rà fọ́yún mi jẹ̀, Ìnu báńkì tí mó òn pawó sí, Lójò ikúnlẹ̀ lẹ̀mi ó ko.</p>	<p>If I see an egg, I will buy it for my foetus to eat If I see a fish, I will buy it for my foetus to eat My foetus is a piggy bank where I am keeping my funds I will reap the rewards on the day I give birth. If I see an egg, I will buy it for my foetus to eat If I see a fish, I will buy it for my foetus to eat My foetus is a piggy bank where I am keeping my funds I will reap the rewards on the day I give birth.</p>
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SG13

<p>Ìmòtótó ló lẹ̀ sẹ̀gun àrùn gbogbo, Ìmòtótó ló lẹ̀ sẹ̀gun àrùn gbogbo, Ìmòtótó ilé, Ìmòtótó aṣọ, Ìmòtótó óúnjẹ̀ àtàyíkà wa, Ìmòtótó ló lẹ̀ sẹ̀gun àrùn gbogbo.</p>	<p>Cleanliness can cure all diseases Cleanliness can cure all diseases Cleanliness in the home Cleanliness of cloths Cleanliness of food and environment Cleanliness can cure all diseases.</p>
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The pragmatic function here is advising pregnant women to eat nutritious meals for good foetus development. Similarly, expectant mothers are also cautioned to maintain good hygiene during this period. SG13 admonishes the women and advocates a clean home, surroundings and bodies in order not to fall victim to different diseases.

As well intentioned as the themes and the pragmatic functions of the antenatal songs may be, the way these messages are passed across are very important. Pregnant women are adults and because of this, there is the need to consider the special characteristics of adults while they are being taught. According to Merriam and Brockett (2007), adult education is any programme that is designed to bring about learning for those whose age, social role and self-perception define them as adults. While the age of some of the pregnant women may not be up to 18 years, their social role and self-perception have defined them as adults. Antenatal programmes can therefore be viewed as adult education programme.

According to Shen, Xue & Zhu (2016), adult learners are self-directed, they have independent minds in taking decisions and they have their other responsibilities. Therefore, they must be actively involved in the learning process. The

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pregnant women were made to stand on their feet to sing and dance and therefore participate actively in the learning process. The singing, dancing, and clapping are exercises that are necessary for pregnant women.

Also, an adult learner utilizes life knowledge and life experiences, which can be seen in the fact that most of the songs at the antenatal clinics are composed with the notes of most of the songs that are performed in churches and folklores. This is similar to the findings of Titus (2019) who posits that most of the antenatal songs are derivatives of religious songs and folk tunes. The songs are in the language of the environment which is Yoruba and some of the lyrics are often humorous. This is done so that the learners can unconsciously internalize the song since it is easy to learn and the rhythm is patterned along the songs that the pregnant women are familiar with and in the language that is spoken by almost everybody in the area. The songs are repeated two to three times so that the women can memorize them and even sing them after the antenatal clinic is over so that the message that is being passed across will remain with them after the clinic is over.

Furthermore, adult learners are goal- and relevancy-oriented. This is demonstrated in the songs sung at the antenatal clinics. The goal of every pregnant woman is to deliver a healthy baby safely and the songs at the antenatal clinics emphasize and buttress this point especially SG9, 10, 11 and 12. The songs at the antenatal clinics clearly contribute to the personal objectives of the pregnant women by motivating them to engage in learning and also participate actively at the clinics.

Moreover, adult learning emphasizes practicality. This means that learning should assist the learners to apply theories to practical issues outside the classroom (clinic). The songs at the antenatal clinics evince this fact and they teach pregnant women on important issues. The songs instruct on what to do, where to do it and the importance of all these actions. SG1 focuses on family planning and where it can be done, while SG 3 and SG 14 focus on breast milk and its importance to the baby. SG4 explains the importance of nutrition to the foetus. SG13 educates them on the importance of hygiene.

Conclusion

Singing has always been a tool for both entertainment and education in Yoruba culture. The use of songs for both education and entertainment is also found at antenatal clinics by health practitioners when pregnant women come for their clinic. The study looks at what is taught and how these messages are passed across with the use of songs at antenatal clinics. The songs are used to teach family planning, exercise, nutrition and cleanliness, breastfeeding, prayers and encouragement. The pragmatic functions of the songs include educating, encouraging, advising, entertaining, warning and praising. The messages in these songs are passed across in a way that are practical, relevant, self-directed, humorous, building on the previous knowledge of the participants. In essence, the health practitioners take into consideration that the pregnant women are adult learners.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, The study recommends that;

- i. the government should intensify awareness and continue to sensitize pregnant women through medical practitioners and nurses on the need for them to always register early and attend antenatal clinics so as to make the period of pregnancy stress free for them.
- ii. The government should also encourage pregnant women to attend antenatal clinics by subsidizing their hospital bills.

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